

Pyridine Derivatives. II. On the Preparation of 4-Chloronicotinic Acid 1-Oxide

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The novel reactions¹⁻³ and the utility of 4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide (Ia) as an intermediate in heterocyclic synthesis³⁻⁵ prompt the publication of this note, which describes optimum conditions for the preparation of this compound.

It has been reported earlier¹ that 4-nitronicotinic acid 1-oxide (I, b) can be converted in high yield by the action of acetyl chloride to 4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide (I, a). Later on it was found² that the above reaction when run at 100°, is accompanied by the formation of significant amounts (15-20%) of 4-hydroxy nicotinic acid 1-oxide (I, c), whereas less

- a, R = Cl
b, R = NO₂
c, R = OH

than 1% of the latter contaminant is formed at 70°. Our earlier experience with this compound^{3,4} and the need for preparing it as a key intermediate for the synthesis of some pyrazolopyridines in our laboratory, necessitated extensive studies on the formation of this compound. In all, 25 experiments were carried out at different temperatures² and time of reflux, using the same proportions of reactants as described by Taylor and Driscoll². It has been found that the compound is produced in the highest yield when the reflux temperature is 66-70° and reflux time is 6 hrs. The contaminant (i.e., 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide, I, c) begins to form when the bath temperature is raised beyond 70°, and it is obtained in 25% yield, when the temperature of the bath is between 86-100°. Between 101 and 105°,

1. E. C. Taylor and A. J. Crovetti, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 214.
2. E. C. Taylor and J. S. Driscoll, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 3141.
3. G. M. Badger and R. P. Rao, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 1399.
4. G. M. Badger and R. P. Rao, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1965, **18**, 379.
5. R. P. Rao and J. N. Singh, *J. Sc. Tech.*, India, 1969, **7**, 126.

the yield of the contaminant seems to depend on the time of reflux (27% at 4 hrs, 38% at 5 hrs of refluxing). Table I describes the ratio of 4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide (I, a) and 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide (I, c) formed at various temperatures and time of reflux.

TABLE I

Yields and physical properties of 4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide and 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide^a

Expt. No.	Temp. °C	Reflux time hr.	Product Composition			
			Fraction I (4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide)		Fraction II (4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide)	
			M.P. °C	% Yield	M.P. °C	% Yield
1.	46—50	4	168	55	—	—
2.	46—50	5	168	55	—	—
3.	46—50	6	168	58	—	—
4.	51—55	4	170	58	—	—
5.	51—55	5	170	63	—	—
6.	51—55	6	170	63	—	—
7.	56—60	4	166	63	—	—
8.	56—60	5	166	63	—	—
9.	56—60	6	166	67	—	—
10.	61—65	4	168	63	—	—
11.	61—65	5	168	63	—	—
12.	66—70	3	168	63	—	—
13.	66—70	4	168	67	—	—
14.	66—70	5	168—70	68(b, c)	—	—
15.	66—70	6	168—70	73—84 ^{b,c}	—	—
16.	71—75	5	176	63	—	—
17.	76—80	5	186	64	—	—
18.	81—85	5	186	63	—	—
19.	86—90	5	188	38	260	25
20.	91—95	4	190	38	260	25
21.	91—95	5	191	38	260	25
22.	96—100	4	195	38	260	25
23.	96—100	5	195	38	260	25
24.	101—105	4	200	38	260	27 ^d
25.	101—105	5	200	25	260	38 ^d

NOTE : a. The proportion of reactants used were similar to that described in the experimental.

b. This yield is average of five experiments.

c. Analyses for 4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide, Found : C, 41.7; H, 2.4; N, 8.0. Calc. for $C_6H_4ClNO_3$: C, 41.5; H, 2.3; N, 8.1,

d. Analyses for 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide, Found : C, 46.4; 46.5; H, 3.6, 3.3; N, 8.8, 9.3. Calc. for $C_6H_5NO_4$: C, 46.45; H, 3.2; N, 9.0,

The method giving the highest yield of the title compound is reported in the Experimental.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 4-Chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide: 4-Nitronicotinic acid 1-oxide (3 g.) was added little by little to acetyl chloride (15 ml) kept in a 50 ml. R.B. flask, which was protected with a calcium chloride-guard tube and cooled in an ice-bath. The flask was then attached to a reflux condenser and the mixture heated with stirring at 66–70° (oil-bath temperature) for 6 hrs. After cooling the reaction mixture to room temperature, the precipitated solid was separated and the solid (Fraction I) as well as the mother liquor (Fraction II) were added in small portions to about 20 to 25 g. of crushed ice and stirred well. After refrigerating overnight, the contents were filtered. Fraction I gave 4-chloronicotinic acid 1-oxide in reasonably pure condition (m.p. 168–170° d). Attempts to recrystallise it from water resulted in its conversion into 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide (m.p. 260° d.).

Fraction II on further concentration gave 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide. In experiments I to 18, the working out of Fraction II gave very small yields of 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide. In experiments 16 to 25, working up of Fraction I gave mixtures of 4-chloro- and 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxides as is apparent from the m.p. of the product. Working up of Fraction II in experiments 19 to 25 gave exclusively 4-hydroxynicotinic acid 1-oxide as is apparent from the m.p. of the product as well as from the elemental analysis. (Table I).

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